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Satisfaction with the Working Condition in the Italian Regions between 2018 and 2022

Between 2018 and 2022, it grew by an amount equal to 3.34%

Istat calculates the value of satisfaction with the work done in the Italian regions. The variable expresses the percentage of employed people who expressed an average satisfaction score between 8 and 10 for the following aspects of the work performed: earnings, career opportunities, number of hours worked, job stability, distance from home to work, interest in Work. The data refers to the Italian regions between 2018 and 2022.

Ranking of the Italian regions by value of satisfaction with the work carried out in the Italian regions in 2022. Trentino Alto Adige is in first place for the value of satisfaction with the work carried out in the Italian regions in 2022 with an amount of 61.9 units, followed by Valle d'Aosta with an amount of 59.3 and from Piedmont with 56.9 units. In the middle of the table are Tuscany with an amount of 51.8 units, followed by Emilia Romagna with an amount of 51.7 units, and Friuli Venezia Giulia with 51.5 units. Basilicata closes the ranking with 40.1 units, followed by Calabria with 39.6 units and Campania with 39.1 units.

Ranking of the Italian regions by percentage change in satisfaction with the work carried out in the Italian regions between 2018 and 2022. Abruzzo is in first place for the value of the percentage change in the work carried out with a change equal to 22.84%, equal to variation from an amount of 39.40 units in 2018 up to a value of 48.40 units in 2022 equal to a value of 9.00 units. Sicily is in second place for percentage change in satisfaction with the work carried out in the Italian regions between 2018 and 2022 with a value of 21.47% corresponding to a change from an amount of 35.40 units up to a value of 43.00. The Marche region is in third place with a percentage change value of 20.00% corresponding to a change from an amount of 43.50 units in 2018 up to 52.20 units in 2022 equal to an amount of 8.70 units. In the middle of the table is Tuscany with a percentage variation of 17.19% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 44.20 units up to a value of 51.80 units equal to an amount of 7.60 units. Sardinia follows with a percentage variation of 17.18% corresponding to a variation of 7.80 units corresponding to an increase from 45.50 units in 2018 up to 53.20 units in 2022. Lazio follows with a percentage variation between 2018 and 2022 corresponding to a value of 16.71% equal to a variation from 43.10 in 2018 up to 50.30 units in 2022 equal to an amount of 7.20 units. Valle d'Aosta closes the ranking with a variation equal to a value of 7.04% corresponding to a variation corresponding to an amount of 7.04% equal to a variation from an amount of 55.40 units up to a value of 59.30 units equal to a variation of 3.90 units. Molise follows with a percentage variation of 5.62% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 49.80 units in 2018 up to a value of 52.60 units in 2022. Trentino Alto Adige follows with a percentage variation corresponding to a variation of 3.34% equal to a variation from an amount of 59.90 units up to a value of 61.90 units equal to 2.00

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units. On average, the value of satisfaction with the work done in the Italian regions grew between 2018 and 2022 from an amount of 44.34 units up to a value of 50.35 units corresponding to a variation of 2.00 units equal to a value by 3.34%.

Satisfaction with the work carried out in the Italian macro-regions between 2018 and 2022. The value of satisfaction with the work carried out in the North grew from an amount of 64.50 units up to a value of 52.80 units in the corresponding 2022 to a variation of an amount of 6.30 units equal to a value of 13.55%. Satisfaction with the work carried out in the North-West grew by 17.84% between 2018 and 2022, going from a value of 45.40 units to a value of 53.50 units or equal to a value of 8.10 unit. Satisfaction with the work carried out in the North-East grew by an amount equal to 7.90% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 48.10 units up to a value of 51.90 units or equal to a variation of 3.80 units. Satisfaction with the work carried out in the Center grew by an amount of 17.58% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 43.80 units in 2018 up to a value of 51.50 units in 2022 equal to a value of 7.70 units. Satisfaction with the work carried out in Southern Italy grew by 16.58% between 2018 and 2022 corresponding to a change from an amount of 38.00 units up to a value of 44.30 units or equal to a value of 6.30 units. Satisfaction with the work carried out in Southern Italy grew by 15.08% between 2018 and 2022 or from an amount of 37.80 units up to a value of 43.50 units equal to a variation of 5.70 units. Satisfaction with the work carried out in the Islands grew from an amount of 38.40 units in 2018 up to a value of 46.00 in 2022 or corresponding to a variation of 7.60 units equal to a value of 19.79%.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. Below we present a clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. Three different clusters are identified:

- *Cluster 1:* Trentino Alto Adige, Valle d'Aosta;
- *Cluster 2:* Basilicata, Calabria, Sicily, Campania, Liguria, Abruzzo, Puglia;
- *Cluster 3:* Friuli Venezia Giulia, Emilia Romagna, Lombardy, Sardinia, Tuscany, Marche, Umbria, Molise, Piedmont, Veneto, Lazio.

Considering the value of the average of the clusters the following ordering results: $C1 > C3 > C2$. It therefore follows that the regions of the Centre-North appear to have a higher value of satisfaction with the work performed than the corresponding value of the southern regions. Liguria is the only northern region that participates in the cluster of southern regions. Molise is the only southern region to be present in Cluster 3, i.e. the Cluster that contains most of the Central-Northern regions.

Conclusions. The value of satisfaction with the work done grew between 2018 and 2022 in all Italian regions. However, there is still a significant difference between the Centre-North and the South. In any case, it must be considered that on average in Italy in 2022 approximately 50.2% of employed people expressed satisfaction with the work performed. Even if this value grew between 2018 and 2022, it turns out that only half of the workforce expresses satisfaction with the work done. It means that the other half of those employed are substantially dissatisfied with the work they do. That is, we should intervene with economic labour policies aimed at improving the conditions of at least 50% of those employed for whom the work is unsatisfactory.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Declaration of Competing Interest. The author declares that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this manuscript. In addition, the ethical issues, including plagiarism, informed consent, misconduct, data fabrication and/or falsification, double publication.

Software. The authors have used the following software: Gretl for the econometric models, Orange for clusterization and network analysis, and KNIME for machine learning and predictions. They are all free version without licenses.

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Appendix

